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Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Imagery System based on Ultra Wideband (UWB) Radar

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Abstract-

Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) systems are among of the wireless or remote sensors which are widely used for accuracy target (object) detection and localization by using electromagnetic radiation. The main job of SAR image formation algorithm is to generate the require scene image. This is done by processing the compressed pulse signal from each aperture position of SAR imaging system. There are two SAR image formation technologies: first one is frequency-domain algorithm, second one is time-domain algorithm for generating the SAR image from the scene. From earlier decades, the common SAR image formation algorithm known was frequency-domain, but nowadays the most very used is Time-domain as also known on the name of Back-projection algorithm and as also this project is based on it. In this paper the Range imaging, cross-range imaging, and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imaging algorithms will be implemented in MATLAB based on the data from the UWB radar. This project of UWB SAR imaging system builds a system with the main goal of forming the SAR images using synthetic aperture radar (SAR) simulations coded in MATLAB.

Key words - Radar, SAR, Radar Cross Section, Radar imaging System, Back-projection (BP) Algorithm

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1. Introduction

Ultra Wideband (UWB) pulse radar is one of the promising techniques for near-field sensing systems. Ultra wideband technology becomes more widely used for near-field object detection. We present an aperture synthetic radar (SAR) system using ultra-wideband (UWB) signals for such applications examples, automated target recognition in non-contact measurement with a high resolution , imaging of buried objects underground , UWB indoor and through-wall imaging radar , UWB stroke diagnosis system , as well as some fundamental investigation of the penetration ability of UWB signals . In many of these applications UWB synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imaging algorithm is used to form an image from the subsurface of the object. However, one drawback with UWB time-domain SAR imaging algorithm is the undesired blurry image of the true object due to the scattered fields of adjacent objects. Since SAR algorithm is only based on the summation at each pixel of all time-delayed signals coming from all scattered fields, the algorithm cannot distinguish the scattered field of the object at this pixel from those scattering of objects at other pixels.

This project has been developed a system that utilizes the techniques of Ultra Wideband (UWB) and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) to produce top view images of a scene using measurements from the side. The system consists of the PulsON P440 radar module, a set of antennas, a moving platform and an imaging algorithm programmed in MATLAB. In general, this project will be based on those two technological components: synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and ultra wide band (UWB). Radar has long been used for military and non-military purposes in a wide variety of applications such as imaging, guidance, remote sensing and global positioning. For many years (decades) the use of Optical methods for collecting data on spacecraft and aircraft have been famous.

Later in 1970s, radar became a standard component in space-borne remote sensing systems. Radar has been proved to be valuable, because of its day and-night capability and the possibility to penetrate foliage, clouds and rain Development of radar as a tool for ship and aircraft detection was started during 1920s. In 1922, the first continuous wave radar system was demonstrated by Taylor. The first pulse radar system was developed in 1934 with operating frequency 60 MHz by Naval Research Laboratory (NRL), US. At the same time, radar systems for tracking and detection of aircraft were developed both in Great Britain and Germany during the early 1930s. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems are radar imaging that exploits the collection of many independent samples of targets in a particular scene to produce intrinsically high-resolution images

and have several key advantages over airborne optical imagers. Because of its high and spatial resolution of UWB synthetic aperture radar (SAR), there are many usages in different applications include intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance, interferometry, foliage penetration, moving target indication, and environmental monitoring.

SAR is often preferred over optical imagers for these applications because its performance is independent of available daylight and visibility. UWB synthetic aperture radars (SAR) are among the latest generation of high resolution imaging radars. Such a radar system usually operates at lower frequency band such as VHF or UHF bands, has exceptionally large fractional bandwidth, and antenna with wide angular beam widths that span tens of degrees. A system has been developed that utilizes the techniques of Ultra Wideband and Synthetic Aperture Radar to produce top view images of a scene using measurements from the side. The system consists of the PulsON P440 radar module, a set of antennas, a moving platform and an imaging algorithm. This thesis will cover all the aspects of the data acquisition part of the system with additionally an analysis on antennas.

As the SAR system operation creates an image from radar by pointing a radar beam approximately perpendicular to the target scene. Phase encoded pulses are transmitted and radar echoes reflected from scene are recorded. The main goal of the SAR imaging algorithm is to generate the 2D SAR image of the target scene from which the x and y coordinates of the targets. In this algorithm of SAR imaging there are some techniques will be applied like Fast Fourier Transformation (fft) for converting data to range and azimuth-frequency domain (range Doppler) and like Hilbert transformation to generate the 2D SAR image. There are several ways that SAR is used; however all methods use a moving system to study or survey a specific surface. For a SAR system to work correctly it is assumed that the radar is traveling at a constant velocity and a constant altitude parallel to the ground [6].

SAR usually uses narrow band microwaves to generate an image. However, recently the impact of UWB signals has greatly increased image resolution. Flyover SAR uses three different survey techniques. These techniques are called spotlighting, strip mapping, and scanning. Synthetic aperture processing is a well-established technology used in a variety of remote sensing applications. Its primary benefit derives from the capability to generate high resolution images, and to do so in conditions unsuited for optical-based methods. For example, good quality synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images can be obtained at night or through obscuring material such as cloud cover. The reason for this of course, is that unlike photography, which makes use of ambient light, radar produces its own illumination, collecting reflected energy for further processing. This provides great flexibility for radar based imaging, as one can choose the operating frequency range to suit the application rather than being restricted to a narrow band of optical frequencies and their associated limitations.

This rail system (moving platform) is designed and implemented to provide accurate positioning of the radar and the antennas along a three meter length. This allows the radar to transmit pulses and acquire a coherently integrated receive signal at a particular radar position. The radar position can then be changed and the transmit/receive process can be repeated at the new position. The major components of the moving platform are stated as follow, a drive actuator, a stepper motor, a stepper drive, a power supply to provide power to the stepper drive, a cart on which the radar and the antennas are mounted on it.

As the current localization technologies like GPS is not sufficient for providing to urban vehicles facilities for localizing the closest things, this SAR imaging algorithm intervene to help to localize the closest things in the roads. In order to achieve this system must be capable of carrying out several tasks: first the system has to be able to move and keep track of at which position each measurement is taken. The second one the system must be capable of sending electromagnetic signals and receive their reflections. Finally the signals that are received have to be processed into an image. These tasks are divided into three groups: hardware group, data acquisition group and imaging group.

2. Synthetic Aperture Radar

A. Radar imaging System

The radar imaging system of this thesis consists of UWB radar and two antennas, a rail system to control the motion of the radar and the antennas, and MATLAB software, executed from a PC, to interface with the radar and the rail system. All components used for this Radar Imaging system such as the radar and the antennas, the rail system, like a radiometer, radar systems use very sensitive receivers to output a voltage that contains information about the target. Unlike a radiometer, the signal that the radar receives does not originate from the target (emission), rather it is a scattered version of a signal transmitted by the radar. Therefore the characteristics of the signal received by radar may be fundamentally different from the radiometer signal. Radar is an acronym for radio detection and ranging.

Detection addresses the question of whether a target is present or changing. Ranging, the ability to measure the range to a target, is possible as radar provides its own illumination (the transmitter) unlike a radiometer that provides no range information. The transmitted radar signal may be coherent, polarized, and modulated in frequency, phase, amplitude, and polarization. In addition, the transmit antenna determines the spatial distribution of the transmitted signal. While radar system measures only the received signal voltage as a function of time, signal analysis enables the extraction of new information about the target including location, velocity, composition, structure, rotation, vibration, etc.

Figure 1: P440 UWB Radar

B. Puls ON P440 UWB Radar

As the figure 1 is shown, Time Domain's PulsON® 440 (P440) modules is a wireless high precision "smart" ranging and radar sensor, ready for OEM integration into a variety of products and applications. This versatile device is a fully coherent UWB transceiver and is driven by FIFE, the company's 6th generation custom UWB silicon chip. FIFE combines two existing semiconductor chips into one chip – lowering cost, reducing the power consumption and physical size by half, and meeting both US and EU transmission regulations for broader worldwide adoption.

The P440 ranging/radar module provides users with exceptional functionality:

- Most precise two-way ranging radio on the market today (accuracy of <2 cm)
- Fully coherent short-range radar offers excellent clutter rejection and 1.4 GHz instantaneous bandwidth □ OEM device capable of operation at industrial temperatures and in high shock/vibration environments.
- As a ranging radio, the P440 uses Two-Way Time-of-Flight (TW-TOF) ranging to precisely measure the distance between two or more P440s. These ranging measurements have an accuracy of 2 cm and are provided at rates up to 125 Hz. Data communications is also supported.
 - Ranging customers get access to a network optimized for TW-TOF measurement. This ranging network can be operated using either the ALOHA or TDMA protocols. A new location engine has been added to support rapid design of user navigation and tracking systems.
 - The P440 can operate as a monostatic, bistatic, or multistatic radar. It provides the resolution required to achieve clutter rejection for operation inside buildings and in other complex environments. It provides both raw and filtered radar scan data as well as detection lists consisting of the distance and amplitude of targets within its scan range.
 - It can provide all four functions (range determination, data transfer, monostatic radar, and multistate radar) simultaneously.
 - It is interoperable with Time Domain's earlier generation equipment (P400, P410, and P412). The hardware is designed to operate over the full industrial temperature range (40°C to +85°C) as well as operate in high shock and high vibration environments.

- The UWB RF emissions are compliant with both the United States Federal Communications Commission (FCC) Part 15 regulations and the European Union ETSI EN 302 065 standard mask.

The P440 is a cost-effective, easy-to-use, and reliable UWB transceiver and is being deployed worldwide by innovators like you to solve difficult collision avoidance, vehicle navigation, and asset tracking problems. In the radar imaging system of this thesis, a MATLAB program is used to configure the desired parameters of the P440 and to command it to transmit pulses and receive return signals. The received electromagnetic signals are sampled by the P440 and the data is saved by the MATLAB program as a data file for later processing.

The Time Domain Corporation has developed a variety of systems that use time modulated ultra wideband (TM-UWB) architecture. This patented PulsON technology uses very short duration (<2 ns) UWB pulses at an average repetition rate of from 10 to 40 MHz. A typical system uses pulses that span 1.4 GHz centered at 2.0 GHz. Because the pulses are pseudo randomly shifted in time, they look like white noise from the point of view of a narrow band receiver, and by distributing energy across such large bandwidths; the spectral energy in any particular narrow band is very low. Channelization may be obtained by using different pseudo-random patterns of pulses for different links. Data is transmitted by time modulation: sending pulses either early or late with respect to the baseline pattern.

C. *Sar Back-Projection Algorithm*

The Back-projection (BP) algorithm is the root of all time-domain algorithms for UWB SAR in image scene construction or formation. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is a class of radar that utilizes platform motion to obtain finer resolution in the along-track dimension than that given by the along-track illumination footprint. However, time-domain back-projection is one class of image formation techniques that does not fall under the frequency domain category. Time domain back-projection, on the other hand, makes few assumptions. The main assumption it makes is that the imaging geometry is known precisely.

A large antenna aperture is required to reconstruct a high-resolution image from radar data collected from a single location. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) relaxes this constraint by collecting data from multiple locations along a platform trajectory using, for example, radar mounted on an airplane or on moving platform known as rail system.

The back-projection algorithm may be successfully employed for many SAR research endeavors not involving considerably large data sets and not requiring time-critical image formation. Execution of both image reconstruction algorithms in MATLAB is explicitly addressed. In particular, a manipulation of the back-projection imaging equations is supplied to show how common MATLAB functions, FFT (fast Fourier transform), may be used for straight-forward SAR image formation. In addition, limits for scene size and pixel spacing are derived to aid in the selection of an appropriate imaging grid to avoid aliasing. Example SAR images generated through use of the back-projection algorithm are provided given four publicly available SAR datasets from the radar mounted on the rail system for sending well the pulse signals to the scene(target).

A distinct advantage of the back-projection algorithm is the ability to form SAR images as phase history is collected, pulse by pulse, and to integrate newly obtained information into the SAR image as it becomes available. Fortunately, the back-projection algorithm lends itself naturally to parallel processing.

A. *Data Collection*

The main goal of processing any image formation algorithm is to retrieve information data from the target by transmit and receive signals and then forming the image of that very point target by processing the signal data. In BP, a synthetic aperture radar image is directly formed from the radar echo data. There is no intermediate step between data acquisition and final image formation in back-projection algorithm technique. In the data collection I have used the tool called Time domain Monostatic Radar Module (MRM) reconfiguration and Evaluation Tool (RET).

As the figure 2 are stated below.

Figure 2: Pulse Signal Scan tab from the Scene

3. Experimental Simulations

A. Data acquisition

By using the csv.file in the MRM logfile plotter code, Map the detection list mapping to scan number and distance are obtained as shown the figure 3.

Figure 3: Map of the three detected targets

MRM logfile shows how to use read MrmRetLog.m. This script prompts the user for a logfile name and plots a "waterfall in figure 4.3" of the motion filtered scans with overplays of detections. In the figure 4.3, the target is between 3-4 meters from the moving platform as the range from the UWB radar which records the scene.

B. Results

In this project the final results of SAR image formation frameworks by back-projection are shown as following:

Figure 4: Back Projection SAR image

4. Conclusions

This project presented the simulation and implementation of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) Imagery system. A moving platform known also on the name of rail system was presented for holding and controlling the location off-the shelf UWB radar on linear moving platform path. The MATLAB was used retrieve the stored csv file data for mapping the detected targets/scene and for generating the back projection SAR image.

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